

THE IMPORTANCE OF LANGUAGE EDUCATION POLICY AND PRACTICE IN STATE EDUCATION SYSTEMS

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Abstract.

Uzbekistan is a multinational country with the Uzbek language as the only official state language. It is noted that in the framework of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On education” and the National Program for Training in the country, a comprehensive foreign languages’ teaching system, aimed at creating harmoniously developed, highly educated, modern-thinking young generation, further integration of the country to the world community, has been created.

Key words. Curricula, further improvement, language education policy, STEAM, professional colleges, modern methods.

Introduction.

During the years of independence, over 51.7 thousand teachers of foreign languages graduated from universities, English, German and French multimedia tutorials and textbooks for 5-9 grades of secondary schools, electronic resources for learning English in primary schools were created, more than 5000 secondary schools, professional colleges and academic lyceums were equipped with language laboratories.

However, we know that analysis of the current system of organizing language learning shows that learning standards, curricula and textbooks do not fully meet the current requirements, particularly in the use of advanced information and media technologies. Education is mainly conducted in traditional methods. Further development of a continuum of foreign languages learning at all levels of education; improving skills of teachers and provision of modern teaching materials are required.

Furthermore, now English is being taught from 1st grade in order to encourage kids to learn English successfully. Lesson hours offered a week have been extended. Additionally, young generation accepted English as a door to better employment and higher social status, as a way to gain prestige and as a sign of ‘distinction’ “ (cited in Nino-Murcia, 2003: p. 121). Therefore, they gave high priority to improve their speaking and writing skills.

However, myriad young generations are making attempts to get internationally recognized certificates like IELTS and TOEFL in order to work and continue their study in other foreign countries. Another different thing is that nowadays teachers are focusing on ameliorating all skills of learners and textbooks are based on improving four skills by using different methods, testing principles and various types of assessments. At the beginning of 2000s years, teachers and textbooks used to work on grammar rules and translation. Nowadays the ways of teaching and learning English are changing day by day in Uzbekistan.

Language policy in Uzbekistan.

The presidents of the Republic of Uzbekistan also signed several laws on deepening the teaching of foreign languages. Islam Karimov, the first president of Uzbekistan signed the 18.75 decrees “On measures to further improvement of foreign language learning system” on December 10, 2012. The law aims to improve teaching English standards in rural areas and other areas. The salary of foreign language

teachers increased by 30 % who worked in rural areas, the salary of teachers who worked in other areas increased 15%.

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev signed a decree "On the establishment of presidential schools". The educational process is conducted in English according to curricula and programs developed in cooperation with foreign educational institutions and based on the "STEAM - Education" program. (Science, Technology, Engineering, Art, Mathematics). Graduates of presidential schools will receive a proper state certificate, as well as a diploma of the corresponding international program (International Baccalaureate, Advanced Placement, or International Advanced Levels), which in turn will allow them to enter foreign universities. Also, the president paid more attention to the opening of branches of foreign universities to improve the role of the English language. For example, one of the initiators of the opening of the Webster University branch is President Shavkat Mirziyoyev.

The importance of learning foreign languages in Uzbekistan.

Today, English is vital especially for those involved in business, academia and commerce. The following provides an overview of the instrumental, interpersonal and innovative function of English in Uzbekistan. Uzbek people realize that English is significant in all regards when it comes to pursuing international education, attaining a good career and keeping up with the rapid pace of world changes. They greatly favor the English language, seeing it as the key to successful and prosperous life.

The role and influence of English in today are gaining a higher speed in the world as well as in Uzbekistan. The main factors for this phenomenon include expanding communication with the world after gaining the independence and increasing speed and scope of information exchange in the global village. The dominant position in the internet space by the language of the published content is firmly held by English, which is a strong motivation to learn English for those who wish to promote their global competences.

Currently, in the Republic of Uzbekistan great attention is given to the radical reorganization of the educational system that will give an opportunity to raise it to the level of modern standards. It is the obligation of the academic communities to deliver the rich cultural and historical heritage of Uzbek people to the world by translating the literature and academic works of our national scholars and ancestors into the English language — a very effective approach to promote the country in the international arena. The people of Uzbekistan also not only that English is the dominant global language at present but also it is crucial tool for achievement of the personal growth better career opportunities and advanced education.

Conclusion.

In conclusion, the educational system has been changed by the government and it is transformed from the old version to the upgraded version. Shavkat Mirziyoyev. In his address to parliament, the President stressed the need for further development of the English language. Therefore, the Ministry of Public Education is implementing a new project called "English speaking nation." The main aim of the project is to use the latest methods of teaching English to young people and improve their knowledge. In the result, 27 teachers visited Uzbekistan in partnership with the US Embassy on this project. They conducted training in English writing in various regions of Uzbekistan.

All in all, today the considerable change is being made particularly in the education system. The methods have changed, grammar-translation method that was a wide-spread and the only method for teaching languages now is mostly being avoided by modern teachers. English language teachers now try to improve the teaching quality by using an integrated approach. All the language skills are now of great importance and believed to be used in communication that is the most important part of language learning.

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